

“Banana” food

“Carrot” food

“Corn” food

- Actinobacteria;c_Actinobacteria;o_Corynebacteriales;f_Corynebacteriaceae;g_Corynebacterium_1
- Actinobacteria;c_Actinobacteria;o_Corynebacteriales;f_Corynebacteriaceae;g_Lawsonella
- Actinobacteria;c_Actinobacteria;o_Micrococcales;f_Micrococcaceae;g_Micrococcus
- Actinobacteria;c_Actinobacteria;o_Propionibacteriales;f_Propionibacteriaceae;g_Cutibacterium
- Firmicutes;c_Bacilli;o_Bacillales;f_Bacillaceae;g_Anaerobacillus
- Firmicutes;c_Bacilli;o_Bacillales;f_Bacillaceae;g_Bacillus
- Firmicutes;c_Bacilli;o_Bacillales;f_Planococcaceae;g_Planococcus
- Firmicutes;c_Bacilli;o_Bacillales;f_Staphylococcaceae;g_Staphylococcus
- Firmicutes;c_Bacilli;o_Lactobacillales;f_Streptococcaceae;g_Streptococcus
- Proteobacteria;c_Alphaproteobacteria;o_Acetobacteriales;f_Acetobacteraceae;g_Roseomonas
- Proteobacteria;c_Alphaproteobacteria;o_Rhizobiales;f_Beijerinckiaceae;g_Methylobacterium
- Proteobacteria;c_Alphaproteobacteria;o_Rhodobacterales;f_Rhodobacteraceae;g_Paracoccus
- Proteobacteria;c_Alphaproteobacteria;o_Sphingomonadales;f_Sphingomonadaceae;g_Sphingomonas
- Proteobacteria;c_Gammaproteobacteria;o_Alteromonadales;f_Alteromonadaceae;g_Rheinheimera
- Proteobacteria;c_Gammaproteobacteria;o_Enterobacteriales;f_Enterobacteriaceae;g_Escherichia/Shigella
- Proteobacteria;c_Gammaproteobacteria;o_Oceanospirillales;f_Halomonadaceae;g_Halomonas
- Proteobacteria;c_Gammaproteobacteria;o_Pseudomonadales;f_Moraxellaceae;g_Acinetobacter
- Proteobacteria;c_Gammaproteobacteria;o_Pseudomonadales;f_Moraxellaceae;g_Enhydrobacter
- Proteobacteria;c_Gammaproteobacteria;o_Pseudomonadales;f_Moraxellaceae;g_Moraxella
- Proteobacteria;c_Gammaproteobacteria;o_Pseudomonadales;f_Pseudomonadaceae;g_Pseudomonas
- Others;c_Others;o_Others;f_Others;g_Others

Microbiota samples from *Drosophila melanogaster* males